

AgroFIND – Agro-meteorological Forecasting INDices

Version 1.1 with ICON-EU data

AgroFIND is the section of the cloud storage system that hosts the materials produced by the Observatory of Agro-Meteo-Climatology of the Council for Agricultural Research and Economics – Research Centre for Agriculture and Environment (CREA-AA). The Observatory has developed a medium-term forecasting system for agrometeorological indices. This section includes data and related forecast maps of various agrometeorological indices, aiming to provide an overview of future agrometeorological conditions across the Italian area, supporting the Ministry of Agriculture (Masaf) and various Agrometeorological Services.

Since January 2025, the indices are forecasted up to +5 days using forecasting data from the ICON-EU atmospheric weather prediction model, developed by the German Meteorological Service (Deutscher Wetterdienst – DWD). Until 2024, the system was based on HRES-ECMWF weather prediction model data (see previous version). ICON-EU is a limited-area model derived from the global ICOSahedral Nonhydrostatic model ICON (Reinert et al., 2024). The chosen configuration uses the regular rectangular grid version of ICON-EU, which has a spatial resolution of 0.0625° Lon/Lat (~6.5 km). Among the four daily forecast runs (00, 06, 12, and 18 UTC) producing 5-day forecasts (+120h), the agrometeorological indices are calculated using the 00 UTC run. The data are organized by variable and forecast interval (hourly up to +78h, then every 3 hours up to +120h) and are available in a public repository, with a dissemination time of approximately 3 hours after model execution. The repository contains a selection of meteorological variables produced by the model. Many of these belong to the surface atmospheric layer where atmosphere-biosphere interactions occur and are therefore of primary agrometeorological interest.

The entire data flow – from near real-time acquisition via https protocol accessing ICON-EU open data services, through daily preprocessing and forecast index computation, to publication as maps – is managed automatically in the CREA cloud infrastructure. This is performed through Python (version 3.6) with dedicated libraries. The ICON-EU meteorological fields used as inputs for index computation are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Meteorological fields from ICON-EU model

Short Name	Definition	Units
t_2m	Temperature at 2m above ground	K
tmin_2m, tmax_2m	Minimum and maximum temperature at 2m above ground ¹	K
relhum_2m	Relative humidity at 2m above ground	%
v_10m	Meridional wind at 10m above ground	m/s
u_10m	Zonal wind at 10m above ground	m/s
aswdir_s	Downward solar direct radiation flux at the surface	W/m ²
tot_prec	Total precipitation (accumulated since model start)	kg/m ²
hsurf	Orography height ² at cell centers above sea level	m

Based on the fields described above, the first step involves estimating daily-scale agrometeorological variables for the 5 forecast days. These data are structured into *dataArrays*.

The field `tot_prec` provides cumulative precipitation starting from the model initialization time (00 UTC). Therefore, daily precipitation values are derived from the last forecasted value (at + 120h) by subtracting iteratively the value at the previous midnight for each day (from the fourth to the first day). The `aswdir_s` field provides solar radiation averaged over the 1h or 3h time interval; daily values are calculated by summing each value weighted by the corresponding interval length (in hours). Minimum and maximum temperatures are directly obtained from `tmin_2m` and `tmax_2m`, while the daily mean temperature is derived from the 24-hour average of `t_2m` field. Maximum, minimum, and mean daily relative humidity values are extracted from `relhum_2m`. Daily wind speed at 10 m is calculated from the `v_10m` and `u_10m` components averaged over 24 hours. These daily variables, expressed in the units required by FAO 56 guidelines (Allen et al., 1998), enable calculation of the

¹ Minima are collected over 6-hourly intervals on all domains. (Prior to 2015-07-07 minima were collected over 3-hourly intervals on the global grid.) Especially in situations with partial snow cover the minimum temperature `tmin_2m` of a grid point and time interval can be much lower than any instantaneous 2 m temperature `t_2m` during that time interval. The reason is that `t_2m` is defined as the average over all tiles of a grid point, while `tmin_2m` is based on the minimum temperature of all tiles. The same applies to `tmax_2m` (Reinert et al., 2024).

² Invariant field.

daily vapor pressure deficit and the reference evapotranspiration (based on the Penman-Monteith formula).

The selected indices were chosen based on three key criteria: their impact on agricultural production (e.g., heavy rainfall, extreme temperatures), their official recognition by the international scientific community (e.g., through the work of the Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices – ETCCDI), and the possibility of calculating them using forecast data alone (Field et al., 2012; IPCC, 2007; WMO and GWP, 2016). This last requirement excluded indices needing historical or measured data (e.g., anomalies), which depend on past records.

The list of daily agrometeorological forecast indices, available up to five days, is shown in Table 2. These indices are presented as national-scale forecast maps (covering the area between 35.0° - 48.0° N and 6.0° - 20.0° E), updated daily, with one map per day for each index. Each map is associated with a unique URL for storage in a public, open-access repository, and is published on the dedicated "AgroFIND" web page accessible via the Agrometeorology and Climatology Observatory website.

Table 2 – List of agrometeorological forecast indices stored in the AgroFIND storage

Acronym	Definition	Units
TX	Maximum daily temperature	°C
TN	Minimum daily temperature	°C
TX35	Very hot days, defined as the number of days with temperature over 35 °C (available from June to September)	days
LFD0	Late Frost Days, defined as the number of days with minimum temperature under 0 °C (available from March to April)	days
DTR	Diurnal Temperature Range, defined as the temperature range between maximum and minimum daily temperatures	°C
RR	Daily precipitation amount, when it overcomes 5 mm	mm
RRc	Precipitation amount, when it overcomes 5 mm per day, accumulated over days from the first to each of the forecast time steps	mm
R20	Very heavy precipitation days, defined as the number of days with precipitation over 20 mm (calculated from the first to each of the forecast time steps)	days
ETo	Daily reference crop evapotranspiration according to the Penman-Monteith equation defined by FAO	mm
EToc	ETo accumulated over days from the first to each of the forecast time steps	mm
CWB	Daily climatic water balance	mm
CWBc	CWB accumulated over days from the first to each of the forecast time steps	mm
VPD*	Vapor pressure deficit	kPa

*Class thresholds were defined according to Moritz et al. (2024).

References

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